

Simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) using 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : The reagent, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT) has been used for the determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} by spectrophotometric method. Second derivative methods have been developed for the determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} using PPDOT when they are present alone. Simultaneous determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in synthetic mixtures was carried out by measuring the amplitude at 482.5 and 441 nm respectively without the need for employing simultaneous equation.

Keywords : Second derivative spectrophotometry, copper(II), nickel(II).

In continuation of our previous work^{1,2}, herein we report, simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) using new reagent viz. 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT) in aqueous medium. The second derivative spectrum of copper(II) complex with PPDOT shows maximum amplitude at 505 nm (peak) and valley at 468 nm and two zero crosses at 441 and 493 nm. At 468 nm, the amplitude (valley) is proportional to the amount of copper(II). Therefore 468 nm was chosen for the determination of copper when present alone. The second derivative spectrum of nickel(II) complex of PPDOT shows maximum amplitude (peak) at 437 nm. Therefore, nickel is estimated at this wavelength when it is present alone. Simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} is carried out by measuring the peak amplitudes at 482.5 and 441 nm respectively.

Results and discussion

The reagent, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone can be easily prepared¹ by condensing 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime with thiosemicarbazide in 1% HCl-ethanol medium. The reagent is a blend of two important functional groups viz. oxime and thiosemicarbazone. This class of oxime-thiosemicarbazones are not exploited much for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. Moreover second derivative methods using this class of reagents are not reported in the literature.

The colour reactions between the metal ions and PPDOT are instantaneous at room temperature. The amplitudes of complexes in the second derivative method were found to be constant for more than 24 h. Maximum colour intensity is observed¹ for both complexes over a wide range of pH. The order of addition of buffer, metal ions [Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}] and reagent has no adverse effect on the derivative amplitudes of complexes.

The zero-order spectrum of metal complexes with PPDOT were recorded in the wavelength region 350–600 nm against reagent blank. The zero-order spectra of a solutions of copper-PPDOT (curve a) and nickel-PPDOT (curve b) complexes in an aqueous acidic buffer medium (pH 6) are shown in Fig. 1. From the zero-order spectrum second derivative spectra were recorded from which analytical wavelengths are ascertained. The second derivative spectra of complexes are also shown in Fig. 1 (curves a' and b'). From the derivative spectra it is noticed that copper complex shows maximum amplitude at 467 nm (valley) and 505 nm (peak) while nickel shows peak at 432 nm. Beyond 482.5 nm nickel complex has zero amplitude. Further at this wavelength copper(II) has an appreciable amplitude. Copper complex has a zero cross at 441 nm while at this wavelength the amplitude of nickel is appreciable and proportional to the concentration of the metal ion. Hence a simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} is carried out by measuring the peak amplitudes at 482.5 nm and 441 nm respectively. Typical spectra are given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Zero-order and second derivative spectra of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} : (a) zero-order spectrum of Cu^{II} -PPDOT [Cu^{II} , $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and PPDOT, $4 \times 10^{-4} M$]; (a') second derivative spectrum of Cu^{II} -PPDOT system [Cu^{II} , $9.6 \times 10^{-5} M$ and PPDOT, $4 \times 10^{-4} M$]; (b) zero-order spectrum of Ni^{II} -PPDOT system [Ni^{II} , $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and PPDOT, $4 \times 10^{-4} M$]; (b') second derivative spectrum of Ni^{II} -PPDOT system [Ni^{II} , $6.4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and PPDOT, $4 \times 10^{-4} M$].

Fig. 2. Second derivative of (a) Cu^{II} -PPDOT system and (b) Ni^{II} -PPDOT system : [Cu^{II} , $9.6 \times 10^{-5} M$; Ni^{II} , $6.4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and PPDOT, $4 \times 10^{-4} M$].

Individual calibration plots are constructed between amplitude of second derivative spectra and concentration of metal ion at 482.5 nm for Cu^{II} and 441 nm for Ni^{II}. The plots are linear obeying the relationships

$$A_{482.5} = 0.0317C + 0.00001$$

(where A = amplitude of second derivative)

$$A_{441} = 0.0446C + 0.0004$$

for copper(II) and nickel(II) respectively. The amplitude is proportional to the metal ion concentration in the range of 0.70–7.6 µg/ml of copper(II) and 0.40–4.50 µg/ml of nickel(II) at 482.5 and 441 nm respectively.

The simultaneous second derivative spectrometric determinations of copper(II) and nickel(II) in synthetic mixture were carried out by employing the recommended procedure. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Simultaneous determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in synthetic mixtures

Taken (µg/ml)		Found ^a (µg/ml)		Error (%)	
Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
2.288	0.939	2.268	0.918	-0.9	-2.2
2.288	1.409	2.233	1.410	-2.4	+0.1
2.288	1.878	2.246	1.826	-1.8	-2.8
2.288	2.348	2.198	2.369	-3.9	-0.9
2.288	2.817	2.249	2.817	-1.7	-
2.288	3.756	2.208	3.810	-3.5	+1.6
1.525	1.409	1.537	1.461	-0.8	+3.7
3.050	1.409	3.121	1.404	-2.3	-0.3
4.575	1.409	4.595	1.409	+0.4	-
5.338	1.409	5.424	1.461	+1.6	+3.7

^aAverage of three determinations.

Interferences : The effect of foreign ions was studied to know the selectivity of the derivative methods. The amount of foreign ion, which brings about change in the amplitude by 2% was taken as the tolerance limit. Interference of various ions was studied with 3.81 µg/ml of copper(II) and 1.88 µg/ml of nickel(II). The results are given in Table 2. It is noticed that all the ions that do not interfere in the zero-order determination of metal ions also do not interfere in the second derivative analyses. The tolerance limit values, in general are higher in the second derivative methods than those in the zero-order determination of metal ions. Nickel(II) which interferes in the zero-order method does not interfere even at 50-fold excess if the determination of Cu^{II} is carried out at 483 nm where Ni^{II} has zero amplitude and Cu^{II} has sufficiently large amplitude. The metal ions such as Cr^{III}

Table 2. Tolerance limit of foreign ions

Sl. no.	Ion added	Tolerance limit (µg/ml)	
		Copper(II)	Nickel(II)
1.	Citrate	2270	1515
2.	Iodate	1910	1530
3.	Tartrate	1775	1185
4.	Iodide	1525	1525
5.	Thiosulphate	1345	900
6.	Sulphate	1155	770
7.	Phosphate	1140	760
8.	Bromide	960	960
9.	Thiourea	760	610
10.	Nitrate	745	495
11.	Ascarbate	700	70
12.	Thiocyanate	695	465
13.	Oxalate	530	705
14.	Chloride	425	425
15.	Fluoride	230	230
16.	W ^{VI}	370	220
17.	Mo ^{VI}	155	16
18.	Cd ^{II}	135	<i>a</i>
19.	Al ^{III}	110	325
20.	Mn ^{II}	65	65 (65)
21.	Cr ^{III}	45 (30)	20 (2.1)
22.	Fe ^{III}	36 (25)	96
23.	Zn ^{II}	2.4 (0.8)	6.5
24.	Co ^{II}	2.1 (0.6)	3.0
25.	V ^V	0.7 (0.6)	3.0 (0.6)
26.	Ag ^I	2.0 (0.7)	1.3
27.	Cu ^{II}	<i>a</i>	50 ^b (1.5)
28.	Ni ^{II}	11.5 (0.1)	-

^aSeriously interferes.

^bDetermination is carried out at 467.5 nm.

Tolerance limit values in parenthesis correspond to zero-order method.

(60 µg/ml); Hg^{II} (54 µg/ml); Fe^{III} (48 µg/ml); Zn^{II} (32 µg/ml); Co^{II} (25 µg/ml) and V^V (18 µg/ml) are tolerable in second derivative determination of copper. Copper(II) which is tolerable only 2.5 times in the zero-order is tolerable 5 times while it is tolerated over 100-fold if the determination is carried at 441 nm where Cu^{II} has zero cross while Ni^{II} has sufficiently large amplitude. Pb^{II} (30 µg/ml); Hg^{II} (12 µg/ml); Ag^I (11 µg/ml); Mo^{VI} (9 µg/ml); Zn^{II} (4 µg/ml); Co^{II} (3 µg/ml) and V^V (2 µg/ml) do not interfere in the second derivative spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II).

Structures of complexes :

Strong bands observed in the IR spectrum of PPDOT at 1609 and 1199 cm^{-1} are respectively assigned to C=N and C=S stretching vibrations. These bands are shifted to lower frequency (10–15 cm^{-1}) in the IR spectra of complexes indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen atom and thioketo sulphur in coordination. Compositions of the complexes are determined by Job's continuous variation method and molar ratio method. Both complexes are found to have 1 : 2 (M : L) composition. Based on above results a general structure (Fig. 3) is tentatively proposed for the complexes in solution.

Fig. 3. Proposed structure for the complexes.

Experimental

Schimidzu 160 A microcomputer based UV visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells was used for all absorbance and amplitude measurements in derivative spectrophotometry. An ELICO LI -120 digital pH meter was used in pH adjustments. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade unless otherwise stated. All solutions were prepared with distilled water. Stock solutions (0.01 M) of copper(II) and nickel(II) were prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of cupric sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate in 250 ml distilled water respectively. The stock solutions were standardized³ and suitably diluted to obtain working solutions of metal ions.

The synthesis and characterization of PPDOT was described earlier. The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 240 mg of the compound in 100 ml of dimethylformamide and the solution was found to be stable for one day. Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid (0.2 M) (pH 4.0–6.5) and ammonium chloride (2 M)-ammonium hydroxide (2 M) (pH 7.0–10.5) were used in the present study.

Recommended procedure :

(a) *Determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) (second order)* : An aliquot of the solution containing copper(II) or nickel(II) in the analytical concentration range (Cu, 0.76–6.10; Ni, 0.47–3.76 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 5.0) and 1 ml of 0.01 M PPDOT solution were mixed in a 25-ml standard flask and the reaction mixture was diluted to the mark with distilled water and second derivative spectra of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with PPDOT complexes were recorded.

Determination of copper : Plots between derivative amplitudes [peak-zero (503 nm); valley-zero (468 nm) and peak-valley (468–505 nm)] and the amount of copper(II) were prepared. The calibration plots are linear and bears the relation $A_{505} = 0.0163C - 0.0031$ and $A_{468} = 0.0648C + 0.0098$; $A_{468-505} = 0.811C + 0.0067$. The equations suggest that the peak-valley method is more sensitive and hence is adopted for the determination of copper.

Determination of nickel : A plot between peak height and the amount of metal ion was prepared. The plot indicates that the peak amplitude is proportional to the metal ion concentration. The calibration plot is linear and obeys the relationship $A_{437} = 0.0476C - 0.0041$.

(b) *Simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}* : An aliquot of solution containing Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in the optimum concentration range, 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.5) and 1 ml 0.01 M PPDOT solution were mixed in 25-ml standard flask and the reaction mixture was made up to the mark with distilled water. The second derivative amplitude was measured at 482.5 and 441 nm and the amounts of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were computed from calibration graphs.

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